

IDENTIFICATION OF BIOLOGICAL MATERIALS OF CATTLE USING GENETIC MARKERS

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Genetic material (DNA) related to cattle is extracted from biological samples provided for research. These samples may include meat samples, skin samples, hair, horns, and bone samples. Specific requirements are set for pieces of animals' muscle or other tissues. The methods of DNA extraction from different biological materials of cattle vary by method. After extraction the concentration of extracted DNA was quantified by using the Qubit 4.0 fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), following the manufacturer's recommended protocols. For the PCR amplification process of the extracted cattle DNA samples, the "COrDIS Cattle" kit was used. The PCR amplification process was performed using the COrDIS Cattle kit protocol. The following amplification requirements are recommended as standard parameters. It is important to control the heating rate during the temperature rise from 59°C to 72°C to be 0.3°C per second. Due to the high complexity of the amplification involving 15 primer pairs, this heating rate is crucial for the optimal efficiency of the reaction.

For obtaining a complete STR profile of the sample, 0.2 nanograms of extracted DNA is sufficient. The optimal amount is 1 nanogram. PCR was performed on the samples using ProFlex PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA) and the PCR products were analyzed using the SeqStudio 8 Flex genetic analyzer (Hitachi, Japan).

After the analysis is completed, it is necessary to evaluate the results of analyzing the positive control sample. The genotype of the obtained positive control sample was compared with the genotype specified in the manual. Since the genotype of the positive control sample completely matched the expected sample, the genotyping of the analyzed samples continued.

Each marker locus in the electropherogram may correspond to one or two PCR products, corresponding to homozygous and heterozygous states. The difference in allele length is usually 2 base pairs, reflecting differences in the number of dinucleotide repeats. To correctly determine the genotype, it is necessary to take into account the nature of the stutter. Stutters are the extra products of microsatellite marker amplification. For dinucleotide markers specific to all loci in the Cordis Cattle set, it is typical for the stutter to be -2 base pairs relative to the main product. The intensity of the stutter signal can reach up to 50% of the intensity of the allele product. If the difference in allele length is 2 base pairs, the stutter of the longer allele overlaps with the shorter allele, significantly increasing the signal level

The results of the conducted research can be effectively used in genetic expertise, as well as in fundamental and applied studies aimed at examining the allele pool status and dynamics of animal populations, which are agricultural objects. It can also contribute to the development of methods for managing the gene pool of breeds. Through the identification of animal biomaterials, it will be possible to effectively organize the breeding of economically valuable animals, increase their productivity, and protect their health.

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